

DEEP DRAWABILITY OF DUAL PHASE STEEL

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ABSTRACT

Dual phase steel had been prepared in this research. From low carbon steel comer. of 0.1% carbon through its heat treatment in the inter critical annealing region ($\alpha+\gamma$) in 800° C. Then quenching it by brine solution to change into a mixture of ferrite and martensite. Also the deep draw ability of dual phase steel had been studied through the quantity of maximum drawing force and total work to drawing and through types of tempering (time tempering and temperature tempering). The results had showed that deep draw-ability was in a time tempering (5) minutes which this time was in lowest max. force and lowest work to the deep drawing, the best temperature degree of tempering was between (150-200)°C.

1.INTRODUCTION

The technique progress of the world made the need of steels sheets become wider. And the previous properties became not enough, so dual phase steel appeared which its main contents a mixture of ferrite and martinsite (1,2).The curve of stress-strain of dual phase steel is continuous and yield point is not clear and the strain hardening rate be very high in a low strains, and the rate of tensile strength to the yield very high in a comparison to ferrite-pearlite steel.(3,4)

As a result to the importance of a deep draw-ability of metal sheets, instability had been studied which it took place through making cups, depend on mechanical property of sheets and to the friction between the Die and the Blank (5)K. Suzaki (6), studied the connection between deep draw-ability and the value of difference property (R) (anisotropy), of metal sheets. It was found that high (R) improving the deep draw-ability. The importance of (R) is being clear thorough earing which it took place as a result of heterogeneous flow.

There were a lot of studies about tempering and ageing for this steel, one of those was the researcher Rashid' study about the affect of tempering on dual phase steels properties which had a vanadium and he noticed a high affect of temperature degree of tempering on dual phase steels properties. The same investigator studied the affect of strain ageing on the mechanic properties for some types of dual phase steel that thorough determine of the losing of strength or ductility (8). Other investigations in this study was what the researcher peng-Heng (9) had done.

2.EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

2.1 Heat Treatment

2.1.1 Inter-critical Annealing

Heat treatment took place in a middle electric furnace kind (ESF1-PID). (The furnace has a highest temperature degree is (1200)°C. To produce dual phase steel which used in the investigation. Low carbon steel com. had been used which had (1.5 mm) as a thick. The quenching to be done, the furnace should be 800°C, this mean the ($\alpha+\gamma$) region and after reached it should wait for half an hour to reach instability. And then round shapes (Blank) were put inside the furnace to annealing time (15) minutes, and quenching in Brine solution which is a mixture of water and a commercial salt (NaCl) and in a concentration of 3 litres of water to half a kilogram of salt.

2.1.2 Tempering Operation.

Tempering operation had been done in the same furnace of Blanks which were drawing them and samples of Tensile test under temperature degrees (50,100, 150, 200, 250, 300)°C and to a tempering times (5, 15, 25) minutes.

2.2 Mechanical Test

2.2.1 Tensile test

A tensile samples had prepared by cutting rectangle sheets towards the rolling of metal to get tensile samples equal to basic diamentions roles (ASIM-E8). All the tensile test experiments were done on tensile test set (Instron 1195) in a strain rate (6.67×10^{-4}) in a cross head speed equal to 2 mm/minute, samples had been full with tensile till broken. And from stress-strain curve determine the tensile strength which had limited in 0.2% that the point of yield wasn't clear for dual phase steel to each sample of test samples and any samples a count the total elongation.

2.2.2 Deep Drawing Test

Use deep drawing Die which had an external diameter (200 mm) and internal diameter giving radial clearance rate 150% with punch of drawing set. And all the deep drawing experiments had been done in a pressure set (Instron 1197) in a speed of (2mm/minutes) by using oil in laboratory temperature degree. Round shapes (Blanks) had pulled off to cylinder cups after they had been put in the drawing set.

Drawing took place in against way. When the set pushed down the pressure punched push up wit it the metal form which flow inside a hole of Die. The connection between force and ductility had taken from the set which through it max. force of deep drawing had counted with tota work which represent the area under the conection which get directly from the set by using planameter. The round shapes of deep drawing had been cut as round circles made from row metal in radius (90 mm) en circle machine cut.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Tempering usually made to get best of forming properties (High ductility) and to get rid of rest stresses which bare in the steel as a result to previous operations, this be clear through table (1). The figure (1) represent the relation between tempering temperature degree and the max. force to deep drawing. It is found that max. force to drawing increase with the increasing of temperature degree in tempering time (5) minutes and (1.9) KN when moving from 50°C to 100°C, the cause behind that may be the increasing in the tensile strength and yield strength as a result of carbon precipitate on the dislocation in ferrite which reduce of movement it or as a result of transmitted of return austenite to the martensite which its features is high strength as a comparison to all the other phases. And then with the increasing

of temperature degree to 150°C. But after that, max. force of deep drawing reduce with till temperature degree 200°C in a high rate (82) KN, here the cause may be most of return austenit transted to martensite, then the concentration of the carbon will be little because of the increasing in the martensite volume this increase its ductility then increase the ability of the forming of the dual phase steel as well as the increasing of temperature degree leads to the increasing in the growing of the ferrite grain this be clear through examining samples by the microscope, after temperature degree 200°C with strength losing. So best tempering temperature degree is between 150-200°C to get best ability of deep drawing. But to study the affect of tempering time notice that the value of max. force of deep drawing increase with the increase of tempering time in all the tempering temperature degrees because of the increase of tensile and yield strength that because of the separation carbon on the dislocation in ferrite which leads to reduce of moving dislocation rate then increase of yield strength. The fig(2) shows the connection between total work of deep drawing and tempering temperature degree with difference in tempering time. These connections took same way to max. force of deep drawing.

4. CONCLUSIONS

1.- Tempering affect with mechanical properties (strength-ductility) of dual phase steel and to give stability to these properties after the operation tempering.

2.- Reduce the ability of deep drawing of dual phase steel wit the increase of tempering time and the best tempering time is (5) minutes.

3.- It is prefered that tempering temperature degree be between (150-200)° to improve the ability of deep drawing of dual phase steel, When Tempeny be in higher temperature degrees than 200° C, hard phase would be dissolve.

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Table (1) The Mechanical properties of Dual phase steel With Different of The Temperature and The Time Tempering.

Tempering Temperature mechanical properties		50	100	150	200	250	300	Time Temp min
		(Mpa) Tensile strength	516	522	515	433	395	
(Mpa) Yield strength	326.1	337.3	330.5	310.0	292.2	271.7		
(%) Total Elong.	25.3	26.1	27.3	28.9	27.5	26.8		
(Mpa) Tensile strength	520	524	516	489	456	413	10min	
(Mpa) Yield strength	332	340.25	336.1	323.3	306.7	290.9		
(%) Total Elong.	23.5	24.6	25.3	28.5	27	26.8		
(Mpa) Tensile strength	528	230	519	496	465	429	15min	
(Mpa) Yield strength	340	342.3	340.15	329.6	299.2	296.32		
(%) Total Elong.	21.2	22.0	22.9	25.6	24.8	24		

Table (2) Chemical composition for low carbon steel .

C%	Mn%	Si%	P%	S%	Cr%	Mo%	V%	Fe%
0.11	0.42	0.77	0.02	0.015	0.06	0.005	0.06	Rem

Fig.(1) Maximum Drawing force for Dual phase steel versus Tempering Temperature at Different Tempering Time .

Fig (2) Total work of Deep Drawing for Dual phase steel Versus Tempering Temperature at Different Tempering Time.

VIBRATION AND DAMPING

